

Fractional Derivatives of Four Types of Matrix Fractional Functions

Chii-Huei Yu

School of Mathematics and Statistics, Zhaoqing University, Guangdong, China

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14199158>

Published Date: 21-November-2024

Abstract: In this paper, based on Jumarie type of Riemann-Liouville (R-L) fractional derivative and a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions, we obtain arbitrary order fractional derivative of four types of matrix fractional functions by using some methods. Matrix fractional Euler's formula and matrix fractional DeMoivre's formula play important roles in this article. Moreover, our results are generalizations of ordinary calculus results.

Keywords: Jumarie type of R-L fractional derivative, new multiplication, fractional analytic functions, matrix fractional functions.

I. INTRODUCTION

Fractional calculus originated in 1695 and almost at the same time as traditional calculus. Fractional calculus is considered to be a useful tool for understanding and simulating many natural and artificial phenomena. It has developed rapidly in different scientific fields in the past few decades, including not only mathematics and physics, but also engineering, biology, economics and chemistry [1-13].

However, fractional calculus is different from traditional calculus. The definition of fractional derivative is not unique. Common definitions include Riemann-Liouville (R-L) fractional derivative, Caputo fractional derivative, Grunwald-Letnikov (G-L) fractional derivative, and Jumarie's modified R-L fractional derivative [14-18]. Because Jumarie type of R-L fractional derivative helps to avoid non-zero fractional derivative of constant function, it is easier to use this definition to connect fractional calculus with traditional calculus.

In this paper, based on Jumarie type of R-L fractional derivative and a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions, we use some techniques to study the following fractional differential problem of four types of matrix fractional functions:

$$\begin{aligned} &({}_0D_x^\alpha)^m [\sinh_\alpha(\rho \cos_\alpha(sAx^\alpha)) \otimes_\alpha \cos_\alpha(\rho \sin_\alpha(sAx^\alpha))], \\ &({}_0D_x^\alpha)^m [\cosh_\alpha(\rho \cos_\alpha(sAx^\alpha)) \otimes_\alpha \sin_\alpha(\rho \sin_\alpha(sAx^\alpha))], \\ &({}_0D_x^\alpha)^m [\cosh_\alpha(\rho \cos_\alpha(sAx^\alpha)) \otimes_\alpha \cos_\alpha(\rho \sin_\alpha(sAx^\alpha))], \\ &({}_0D_x^\alpha)^m [\sinh_\alpha(\rho \cos_\alpha(sAx^\alpha)) \otimes_\alpha \sin_\alpha(\rho \sin_\alpha(sAx^\alpha))], \end{aligned}$$

where $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, ρ, s are real numbers, m is any positive integer, and A is a real matrix. Matrix fractional Euler's formula and matrix fractional DeMoivre's formula play important roles in this paper. In addition, our results are generalizations of classical calculus results.

II. PRELIMINARIES

At first, we introduce the fractional derivative used in this paper.

Definition 2.1 ([19]): Let $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and x_0 be a real number. The Jumarie's modified Riemann-Liouville (R-L) α -fractional derivative is defined by

$$({}_{x_0}D_x^\alpha)[f(x)] = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \frac{d}{dx} \int_{x_0}^x \frac{f(t)-f(x_0)}{(x-t)^\alpha} dt, \quad (1)$$

where $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is the gamma function. On the other hand, for any positive integer m , we define $({}_{x_0}D_x^\alpha)^m[f(x)] = ({}_{x_0}D_x^\alpha)({}_{x_0}D_x^\alpha) \cdots ({}_{x_0}D_x^\alpha)[f(x)]$, the m -th order α -fractional derivative of $f(x)$.

Proposition 2.2 ([20]): If α, β, x_0, C are real numbers and $\beta \geq \alpha > 0$, then

$$({}_{x_0}D_x^\alpha)[(x - x_0)^\beta] = \frac{\Gamma(\beta+1)}{\Gamma(\beta-\alpha+1)}(x - x_0)^{\beta-\alpha}, \tag{2}$$

and

$$({}_{x_0}D_x^\alpha)[C] = 0. \tag{3}$$

In the following, we introduce the definition of fractional analytic function.

Definition 2.3 ([21]): If x, x_0 , and a_k are real numbers for all k , $x_0 \in (a, b)$, and $0 < \alpha \leq 1$. If the function $f_\alpha: [a, b] \rightarrow R$ can be expressed as an α -fractional power series, i.e., $f_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)}(x - x_0)^{n\alpha}$ on some open interval containing x_0 , then we say that $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ is α -fractional analytic at x_0 . Furthermore, if $f_\alpha: [a, b] \rightarrow R$ is continuous on closed interval $[a, b]$ and it is α -fractional analytic at every point in open interval (a, b) , then f_α is called an α -fractional analytic function on $[a, b]$.

Next, a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions is introduced.

Definition 2.4 ([22]): Let $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and x_0 be a real number. If $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ and $g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ are two α -fractional analytic functions defined on an interval containing x_0 ,

$$f_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)}(x - x_0)^{n\alpha}, \tag{4}$$

$$g_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{b_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)}(x - x_0)^{n\alpha}. \tag{5}$$

Then we define

$$\begin{aligned} & f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha g_\alpha(x^\alpha) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)}(x - x_0)^{n\alpha} \otimes_\alpha \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{b_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)}(x - x_0)^{n\alpha} \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{1}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} \left(\sum_{m=0}^n \binom{n}{m} a_{n-m} b_m \right) (x - x_0)^{n\alpha}. \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Equivalently,

$$\begin{aligned} & f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha g_\alpha(x^\alpha) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{a_n}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}(x - x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n} \otimes_\alpha \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{b_n}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}(x - x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n} \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{1}{n!} \left(\sum_{m=0}^n \binom{n}{m} a_{n-m} b_m \right) \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}(x - x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n}. \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

Definition 2.5 ([23]): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$, $g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ are two α -fractional analytic functions defined on an interval containing x_0 ,

$$f_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)}(x - x_0)^{n\alpha} = \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{a_n}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}(x - x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n}, \tag{8}$$

$$g_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{b_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)}(x - x_0)^{n\alpha} = \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{b_n}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}(x - x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n}. \tag{9}$$

The compositions of $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ and $g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ are defined by

$$(f_\alpha \circ g_\alpha)(x^\alpha) = f_\alpha(g_\alpha(x^\alpha)) = \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{a_n}{n!} (g_\alpha(x^\alpha))^{\otimes_\alpha n}, \tag{10}$$

and

$$(g_\alpha \circ f_\alpha)(x^\alpha) = g_\alpha(f_\alpha(x^\alpha)) = \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{b_n}{n!} (f_\alpha(x^\alpha))^{\otimes_\alpha n}. \tag{11}$$

Definition 2.6 ([24]): Let $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and $f_\alpha(x^\alpha), g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ be two α -fractional analytic functions. Then $(f_\alpha(x^\alpha))^{\otimes \alpha n} = f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha \dots \otimes_\alpha f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ is called the n th power of $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$.

Definition 2.7: If the complex number $z = p + iq$, where p, q are real numbers, and $i = \sqrt{-1}$. p , the real part of z , is denoted by $\text{Re}(z)$; q the imaginary part of z , is denoted by $\text{Im}(z)$.

Definition 2.8 ([25]): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, t is a real number, and A is a matrix. The matrix α -fractional exponential function, matrix α -fractional cosine function, and matrix α -fractional sine function are defined as follows:

$$E_\alpha(tAx^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^\infty (tA)^n \frac{x^{n\alpha}}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} = \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{1}{n!} \left(tA \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes \alpha n}, \tag{12}$$

$$\cos_\alpha(tAx^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^\infty (tA)^{2n} \frac{(-1)^n x^{2n\alpha}}{\Gamma(2n\alpha+1)} = \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{(-1)^n}{(2n)!} \left(tA \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes \alpha 2n}, \tag{13}$$

$$\sin_\alpha(tAx^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^\infty (tA)^{2n+1} \frac{(-1)^n x^{(2n+1)\alpha}}{\Gamma((2n+1)\alpha+1)} = \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{(-1)^n}{(2n+1)!} \left(tA \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes \alpha (2n+1)}. \tag{14}$$

In addition, the matrix α -fractional hyperbolic cosine function and matrix α -fractional hyperbolic sine function are defined as follows:

$$\cosh_\alpha(tAx^\alpha) = \frac{1}{2} [E_\alpha(tAx^\alpha) + E_\alpha(-tAx^\alpha)] = \sum_{n=0}^\infty (tA)^{2n} \frac{x^{2n\alpha}}{\Gamma(2n\alpha+1)} = \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{1}{(2n)!} \left(tA \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes \alpha 2n}, \tag{15}$$

and

$$\sinh_\alpha(tAx^\alpha) = \frac{1}{2} [E_\alpha(tAx^\alpha) - E_\alpha(-tAx^\alpha)] = \sum_{n=0}^\infty (tA)^{2n+1} \frac{x^{(2n+1)\alpha}}{\Gamma((2n+1)\alpha+1)} = \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{1}{(2n+1)!} \left(tA \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes \alpha (2n+1)}. \tag{16}$$

Theorem 2.9 (matrix fractional Euler’s formula)([26]): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and A is a real matrix, then

$$E_\alpha(iAx^\alpha) = \cos_\alpha(Ax^\alpha) + i \sin_\alpha(Ax^\alpha). \tag{17}$$

Theorem 2.10 (matrix fractional DeMoivre’s formula)([27]): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, p is an integer, and A is a real matrix, then

$$[\cos_\alpha(Ax^\alpha) + i \sin_\alpha(Ax^\alpha)]^{\otimes \alpha p} = \cos_\alpha(pAx^\alpha) + i \sin_\alpha(pAx^\alpha). \tag{18}$$

Definition 2.11: The smallest positive real number T_α such that $E_\alpha(iT_\alpha) = 1$, is called the period of $E_\alpha(ix^\alpha)$.

III. MAIN RESULTS

In this section, we use some methods to obtain arbitrary order fractional derivative of four types of matrix fractional functions. At first, two lemmas are needed.

Lemma 3.1: If $0 < \alpha \leq 1, \rho, s$ are real numbers, and A is a real matrix, then

$$\begin{aligned} & \sinh_\alpha(\rho E_\alpha(isAx^\alpha)) \\ &= \sinh_\alpha(\rho \cos_\alpha(sAx^\alpha)) \otimes_\alpha \cos_\alpha(\rho \sin_\alpha(sAx^\alpha)) + i \cdot \cosh_\alpha(\rho \cos_\alpha(sAx^\alpha)) \otimes_\alpha \sin_\alpha(\rho \sin_\alpha(sAx^\alpha)). \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \cosh_\alpha(\rho E_\alpha(isAx^\alpha)) \\ &= \cosh_\alpha(\rho \cos_\alpha(sAx^\alpha)) \otimes_\alpha \cos_\alpha(\rho \sin_\alpha(sAx^\alpha)) + i \cdot \sinh_\alpha(\rho \cos_\alpha(sAx^\alpha)) \otimes_\alpha \sin_\alpha(\rho \sin_\alpha(sAx^\alpha)). \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

Proof By matrix fractional Euler’s formula and matrix fractional DeMoivre’s formula,

$$\begin{aligned} & \sinh_\alpha(\rho E_\alpha(isAx^\alpha)) \\ &= \sinh_\alpha(\rho \cos_\alpha(sAx^\alpha) + i \cdot \rho \sin_\alpha(sAx^\alpha)) \\ &= \sinh_\alpha(\rho \cos_\alpha(sAx^\alpha)) \otimes_\alpha \cosh_\alpha(i \rho \sin_\alpha(sAx^\alpha)) + \cosh_\alpha(\rho \cos_\alpha(sAx^\alpha)) \otimes_\alpha \sinh_\alpha(i \rho \sin_\alpha(sAx^\alpha)) \end{aligned}$$

$$= \sinh_{\alpha}(\rho \cos_{\alpha}(sAx^{\alpha})) \otimes_{\alpha} \cos_{\alpha}(\rho \sin_{\alpha}(sAx^{\alpha})) + i \cdot \cosh_{\alpha}(\rho \cos_{\alpha}(sAx^{\alpha})) \otimes_{\alpha} \sin_{\alpha}(\rho \sin_{\alpha}(sAx^{\alpha})).$$

And

$$\begin{aligned} & \cosh_{\alpha}(\rho E_{\alpha}(isAx^{\alpha})) \\ &= \cosh_{\alpha}(\rho \cos_{\alpha}(sAx^{\alpha}) + i \cdot \rho \sin_{\alpha}(sAx^{\alpha})) \\ &= \cosh_{\alpha}(\rho \cos_{\alpha}(sAx^{\alpha})) \otimes_{\alpha} \cosh_{\alpha}(i \rho \sin_{\alpha}(sAx^{\alpha})) + \sinh_{\alpha}(\rho \cos_{\alpha}(sAx^{\alpha})) \otimes_{\alpha} \sinh_{\alpha}(i \rho \sin_{\alpha}(sAx^{\alpha})) \\ &= \cosh_{\alpha}(\rho \cos_{\alpha}(sAx^{\alpha})) \otimes_{\alpha} \cos_{\alpha}(\rho \sin_{\alpha}(sAx^{\alpha})) + i \cdot \sinh_{\alpha}(\rho \cos_{\alpha}(sAx^{\alpha})) \otimes_{\alpha} \sin_{\alpha}(\rho \sin_{\alpha}(sAx^{\alpha})). \quad \text{q.e.d.} \end{aligned}$$

Lemma 3.2: If $0 < \alpha \leq 1, \rho, s$ are real numbers, and A is a real matrix, then

$$\sinh_{\alpha}(\rho E_{\alpha}(isAx^{\alpha})) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n+1)!} \rho^{2n+1} [\cos_{\alpha}((2n+1)sAx^{\alpha}) + i \cdot \sin_{\alpha}((2n+1)sAx^{\alpha})], \quad (21)$$

$$\cosh_{\alpha}(\rho E_{\alpha}(isAx^{\alpha})) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n)!} \rho^{2n} [\cos_{\alpha}(2nsAx^{\alpha}) + i \cdot \sin_{\alpha}(2nsAx^{\alpha})]. \quad (22)$$

Proof $\sinh_{\alpha}(\rho E_{\alpha}(isAx^{\alpha}))$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n+1)!} (\rho E_{\alpha}(isAx^{\alpha}))^{\otimes_{\alpha} (2n+1)} \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n+1)!} \rho^{2n+1} E_{\alpha}(i(2n+1)sAx^{\alpha}) \quad (\text{by matrix fractional DeMoivre's formula}) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n+1)!} \rho^{2n+1} [\cos_{\alpha}((2n+1)sAx^{\alpha}) + i \cdot \sin_{\alpha}((2n+1)sAx^{\alpha})]. \end{aligned}$$

And

$$\begin{aligned} & \cosh_{\alpha}(\rho E_{\alpha}(isAx^{\alpha})) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n)!} (\rho E_{\alpha}(isAx^{\alpha}))^{\otimes_{\alpha} 2n} \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n)!} \rho^{2n} E_{\alpha}(i2nsAx^{\alpha}) \quad (\text{by matrix fractional DeMoivre's formula}) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n)!} \rho^{2n} [\cos_{\alpha}(2nsAx^{\alpha}) + i \cdot \sin_{\alpha}(2nsAx^{\alpha})]. \quad \text{q.e.d.} \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3.3: If $0 < \alpha \leq 1, \rho, s$ are real numbers, m is any positive integer, A is a real matrix, and E is the unit matrix, then

$$\begin{aligned} & ({}_0D_x^{\alpha})^m [\sinh_{\alpha}(\rho \cos_{\alpha}(sAx^{\alpha})) \otimes_{\alpha} \cos_{\alpha}(\rho \sin_{\alpha}(sAx^{\alpha}))] \\ &= (sA)^m \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n+1)!} \rho^{2n+1} (2n+1)^m \cos_{\alpha} \left((2n+1)sAx^{\alpha} + m \cdot \frac{T_{\alpha}}{4} E \right), \quad (23) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & ({}_0D_x^{\alpha})^m [\cosh_{\alpha}(\rho \cos_{\alpha}(sAx^{\alpha})) \otimes_{\alpha} \sin_{\alpha}(\rho \sin_{\alpha}(sAx^{\alpha}))] \\ &= (sA)^m \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n+1)!} \rho^{2n+1} (2n+1)^m \sin_{\alpha} \left((2n+1)sAx^{\alpha} + m \cdot \frac{T_{\alpha}}{4} E \right), \quad (24) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & ({}_0D_x^{\alpha})^m [\cosh_{\alpha}(\rho \cos_{\alpha}(sAx^{\alpha})) \otimes_{\alpha} \cos_{\alpha}(\rho \sin_{\alpha}(sAx^{\alpha}))] \\ &= (sA)^m \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n)!} \rho^{2n} (2n)^m \cos_{\alpha} \left(2nsAx^{\alpha} + m \cdot \frac{T_{\alpha}}{4} E \right), \quad (25) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & ({}_0D_x^{\alpha})^m [\sinh_{\alpha}(\rho \cos_{\alpha}(sAx^{\alpha})) \otimes_{\alpha} \sin_{\alpha}(\rho \sin_{\alpha}(sAx^{\alpha}))] \\ &= (sA)^m \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n)!} \rho^{2n} (2n)^m \sin_{\alpha} \left(2nsAx^{\alpha} + m \cdot \frac{T_{\alpha}}{4} E \right). \quad (26) \end{aligned}$$

Proof By Lemma 3.1 and Lemma 3.2,

$$({}_0D_x^{\alpha})^m [\sinh_{\alpha}(\rho \cos_{\alpha}(sAx^{\alpha})) \otimes_{\alpha} \cos_{\alpha}(\rho \sin_{\alpha}(sAx^{\alpha}))]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= ({}_0D_x^\alpha)^m [\operatorname{Re}\{sinh_\alpha(\rho E_\alpha(isAx^\alpha))\}] \\
 &= \operatorname{Re}\left\{({}_0D_x^\alpha)^m [sinh_\alpha(\rho E_\alpha(isAx^\alpha))]\right\} \\
 &= \operatorname{Re}\left\{({}_0D_x^\alpha)^m \left[\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n+1)!} \rho^{2n+1} [\cos_\alpha((2n+1)sAx^\alpha) + i \cdot \sin_\alpha((2n+1)sAx^\alpha)]\right]\right\} \\
 &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n+1)!} \rho^{2n+1} (2n+1)^m (sA)^m \cos_\alpha\left((2n+1)sAx^\alpha + m \cdot \frac{T_\alpha}{4} E\right) \\
 &= (sA)^m \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n+1)!} \rho^{2n+1} (2n+1)^m \cos_\alpha\left((2n+1)sAx^\alpha + m \cdot \frac{T_\alpha}{4} E\right). \\
 &\quad ({}_0D_x^\alpha)^m [\cosh_\alpha(\rho \cos_\alpha(sAx^\alpha)) \otimes_\alpha \sin_\alpha(\rho \sin_\alpha(sAx^\alpha))] \\
 &= ({}_0D_x^\alpha)^m [\operatorname{Im}\{sinh_\alpha(\rho E_\alpha(isAx^\alpha))\}] \\
 &= \operatorname{Im}\left\{({}_0D_x^\alpha)^m [sinh_\alpha(\rho E_\alpha(isAx^\alpha))]\right\} \\
 &= \operatorname{Im}\left\{({}_0D_x^\alpha)^m \left[\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n+1)!} \rho^{2n+1} [\cos_\alpha((2n+1)sAx^\alpha) + i \cdot \sin_\alpha((2n+1)sAx^\alpha)]\right]\right\} \\
 &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n+1)!} \rho^{2n+1} (2n+1)^m (sA)^m \sin_\alpha\left((2n+1)sAx^\alpha + m \cdot \frac{T_\alpha}{4} E\right) \\
 &= (sA)^m \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n+1)!} \rho^{2n+1} (2n+1)^m \sin_\alpha\left((2n+1)sAx^\alpha + m \cdot \frac{T_\alpha}{4} E\right). \\
 &\quad ({}_0D_x^\alpha)^m [\cosh_\alpha(\rho \cos_\alpha(sAx^\alpha)) \otimes_\alpha \cos_\alpha(\rho \sin_\alpha(sAx^\alpha))] \\
 &= ({}_0D_x^\alpha)^m [\operatorname{Re}\{cosh_\alpha(\rho E_\alpha(isAx^\alpha))\}] \\
 &= \operatorname{Re}\left\{({}_0D_x^\alpha)^m [cosh_\alpha(\rho E_\alpha(isAx^\alpha))]\right\} \\
 &= \operatorname{Re}\left\{({}_0D_x^\alpha)^m \left[\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n)!} \rho^{2n} [\cos_\alpha(2nsAx^\alpha) + i \cdot \sin_\alpha(2nsAx^\alpha)]\right]\right\} \\
 &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n)!} \rho^{2n} (2n)^m (sA)^m \cos_\alpha\left(2nsAx^\alpha + m \cdot \frac{T_\alpha}{4} E\right) \\
 &= (sA)^m \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n)!} \rho^{2n} (2n)^m \cos_\alpha\left(2nsAx^\alpha + m \cdot \frac{T_\alpha}{4} E\right).
 \end{aligned}$$

Finally,

$$\begin{aligned}
 &({}_0D_x^\alpha)^m [sinh_\alpha(\rho \cos_\alpha(sAx^\alpha)) \otimes_\alpha \sin_\alpha(\rho \sin_\alpha(sAx^\alpha))] \\
 &= ({}_0D_x^\alpha)^m [\operatorname{Im}\{cosh_\alpha(\rho E_\alpha(isAx^\alpha))\}] \\
 &= \operatorname{Im}\left\{({}_0D_x^\alpha)^m [cosh_\alpha(\rho E_\alpha(isAx^\alpha))]\right\} \\
 &= \operatorname{Im}\left\{({}_0D_x^\alpha)^m \left[\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n)!} \rho^{2n} [\cos_\alpha(2nsAx^\alpha) + i \cdot \sin_\alpha(2nsAx^\alpha)]\right]\right\} \\
 &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n)!} \rho^{2n} (2n)^m (sA)^m \sin_\alpha\left(2nsAx^\alpha + m \cdot \frac{T_\alpha}{4} E\right) \\
 &= (sA)^m \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n)!} \rho^{2n} (2n)^m \sin_\alpha\left(2nsAx^\alpha + m \cdot \frac{T_\alpha}{4} E\right). \qquad \text{q.e.d.}
 \end{aligned}$$

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, based on Jumarie type of R-L fractional derivative and a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions, we find arbitrary order fractional derivative of four types of matrix fractional functions by using some methods. In fact, our results are generalizations of traditional calculus results. In the future, we will continue to use Jumarie type of R-L fractional derivative and the new multiplication of fractional analytic functions to study the problems in fractional differential equations and applied mathematics.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. Fallahgoul, S. M. Focardi, and F. Fabozzi, *Fractional Calculus and Fractional Processes with Applications to Financial Economics*, Springer Briefs in Applied Sciences and Technology, Academic Press, London, 2016.
- [2] R. Hilfer, Ed., *Applications of fractional calculus in physics*, World Scientific Publishing, Singapore, 2000.
- [3] M. Teodor, Atanacković, Stevan Pilipović, Bogoljub Stanković, Dušan Zorica, *Fractional Calculus with Applications in Mechanics: Vibrations and Diffusion Processes*, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 2014.
- [4] Mohd. Farman Ali, Manoj Sharma, Renu Jain, *An application of fractional calculus in electrical engineering*, *Advanced Engineering Technology and Application*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 41-45, 2016.
- [5] V. E. Tarasov, *Mathematical economics: application of fractional calculus*, *Mathematics*, vol. 8, no. 5, 660, 2020.
- [6] R. L. Magin, *Fractional calculus models of complex dynamics in biological tissues*, *Computers & Mathematics with Applications*, vol. 59, no. 5, pp. 1586-1593, 2010.
- [7] J. F. Douglas, *Some applications of fractional calculus to polymer science*, *Advances in chemical physics*, Vol 102, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 2007.
- [8] R. Caponetto, G. Dongola, L. Fortuna, I. Petras, *Fractional order systems: modeling and control applications*, Singapore: World Scientific, 2010.
- [9] V. V. Uchaikin, *Fractional Derivatives for Physicists and Engineers*, Vol. 1, Background and Theory, Vol 2, Application, Springer, 2013.
- [10] R. C. Koeller, *Applications of fractional calculus to the theory of viscoelasticity*, *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, vol. 51, no. 2, 299, 1984.
- [11] R. Almeida, N. R. Bastos, and M. T. T. Monteiro, *Modeling some real phenomena by fractional differential equations*, *Mathematical Methods in the Applied Sciences*, vol. 39, no. 16, pp. 4846-4855, 2016.
- [12] B. M. Vinagre and YangQuan Chen, *Fractional calculus applications in automatic control and robotics*, 41st IEEE Conference on decision and control Tutorial Workshop #2, Las Vegas, Desember 2002.
- [13] F. Duarte and J. A. T. Machado, *Chaotic phenomena and fractional-order dynamics in the trajectory control of redundant manipulators*, *Nonlinear Dynamics*, vol. 29, no. 1-4, pp. 315-342, 2002.
- [14] K. Diethelm, *The Analysis of Fractional Differential Equations*, Springer-Verlag, 2010.
- [15] K. B. Oldham and J. Spanier, *The Fractional Calculus*, Academic Press, Inc., 1974.
- [16] S. Das, *Functional Fractional Calculus*, 2nd ed. Springer-Verlag, 2011.
- [17] I. Podlubny, *Fractional Differential Equations*, Academic Press, San Diego, Calif, USA, 1999.
- [18] K. S. Miller, B. Ross, *An Introduction to the Fractional Calculus and Fractional Differential Equations*, John Wiley & Sons, New York, USA, 1993.
- [19] C. -H. Yu, *Sum of some fractional analytic functions*, *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technology Research*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 6-10, 2023.
- [20] C. -H. Yu, *Exact solutions of some fractional power series*, *International Journal of Engineering Research and Reviews*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 36-40, 2023.
- [21] C. -H. Yu, *Evaluating fractional derivatives of two matrix fractional functions based on Jumarie type of Riemann-Liouville fractional derivative*, *International Journal of Engineering Research and Reviews*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 39-43, 2024.
- [22] C. -H. Yu, *Studying three types of matrix fractional integrals*, *International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Innovations*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 35-39, 2024.

- [23] C. -H, Yu, Fractional partial differential problem of some matrix two-variables fractional functions, International Journal of Mechanical and Industrial Technology, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 6-13, 2024.
- [24] C. -H, Yu, Study of two matrix fractional integrals by using differentiation under fractional integral sign, International Journal of Civil and Structural Engineering Research, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 24-30, 2024.
- [25] C. -H, Yu, Study of some type of matrix fractional integral, International Journal of Recent Research in Civil and Mechanical Engineering, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 5-8, 2024.
- [26] C. -H, Yu, Evaluating fractional Fourier series expansions of two types of matrix fractional functions, International Journal of Novel Research in Physics Chemistry & Mathematics, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 28-32, 2024.
- [27] C. -H, Yu, Research on fractional derivatives of some matrix fractional functions, International Journal of Electrical and Electronics Research, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 11-15, 2024.